

5-SHO‘BA TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO TEACH ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Xaydarova Shoira Tohirovna

Jizzak branch of the national university of Uzbekistan

shoiraxaydarova@mail.ru

Abstract: This article discusses the difficulties encountered in the process of teaching English and how to overcome them. The issue of finding a solution to the problem is considered.

Key words: Pronunciation, imitation, phonetics, communication.

Today, the demand for language learning is increasing sharply. Language learning has become a social need and has risen to the level of state policy. As a practical proof of this, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No. 1875 "Foreign It is permissible to cite the Decision on measures to further improve the language learning system. After the decision came into force, the English language was taught in the primary grades. In the first grade, English is taught orally, that is, with the help of songs and poems. Starting from the second grade, students are taught to form sentences using letters, words, and words. In the third and fourth grades, students are expected to begin a more complex process of communicating in English. One of the unique aspects of learning English is its pronunciation, and words in this language are not read the way they are written as in Uzbek. This, in turn, causes several difficulties. The process of teaching a foreign language to elementary school students is quite complicated, and it is mainly done based on imitation.

Imitation, on the other hand, causes the student to rely too much on the teacher, and it becomes difficult for him to read words independently.

To develop students' English speaking skills, we should pay attention to pronunciation first. "Foreign language pronunciation is taught using imitative and analytical methods," Jamal Jalolov's book "Foreign Language Teaching Methodology" states.

The imitative method is natural and simple. However, it is based on the unconscious acquisition of the language, including its pronunciation. Without understanding the phonetic units, it is called imitation. If it is said or said, imitation learning occurs. In school textbooks, exercises for teaching pronunciation are mainly carried out using the imitation method. The student can only read the words that the teacher has taught him to read, that is, he cannot explain why he pronounces the word that way. A sharp hearing is required from the student to master imitation correctly.

Imitation puts the task of correct pronunciation on the teacher. If the teacher himself pronounces the word incorrectly,

The analytical method, on the other hand, requires working with the participation of the mind, as a result of which the logical thinking of students is developed. The student understands and understands pronunciation units through analysis. It is acceptable to use a certain rule, and analysis when teaching a foreign language sound or pronunciation phenomenon that does not resemble a phonetic unit in the student's language experience.

In this process, the student can pronounce words independently without the help of the teacher. As an example of this, let's pay attention to the reading of some consonant letters that come together at the beginning and end of a word in English. In some cases, one of the consonant letters that come together is lost in pronunciation, or on the contrary, both letters are pronounced as a completely different sound. The combination of the letters ph together represents the sound f. So, it is correct to pronounce the word phone as foun.

The reading of letters is represented by transcription. The sounds are reflected in the text using transcription symbols. The reading of the words based on the correct pronunciation standards is given using square brackets as follows

In conclusion, students are not required to learn English phonetics fully to learn to pronounce words correctly. When they learn how letters are represented in writing using transcription symbols, they develop the skills of correct reading and can pronounce words independently without the help of a teacher. In addition to the student's school textbooks, if a guide called "Rules of correct reading in English" is included, it will make it easier for students and teachers. Even parents can use this guide. they can also use it to help their children prepare for English lessons. Usually, parents find it difficult to help their children in the process of preparing English lessons.

List of references used:

1. Decision of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abdugyanovich Karimov dated December 10, 2012 PQ 1875

2. J. Jalolov "Methodology of foreign language teaching" 2012 "Teacher" publishing house

3. Sh.Alimov and A.Ismailov "Methodology of foreign language teaching" Text of lectures Andijan-2007

4. Xaydarova, S. (2021). CHET TILI FANLARINI O‘ QITILISHIDA INNOVATSION METODLAR. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI.

5. Xaydarova, S. (2020). BOSHLANG‘ ICH SINFLARDA INGLIZ TILI TALAFFUZINI O‘ RGATISHDA MULTIMEDIA VOSITALARINING AHAMIYATI. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. Internet materials

6. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA HORIJYIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. 2022. T. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.